

Temperature Dependence of Interchange Energy

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Temperature dependence of interchange energy has been examined from theoretical considerations. The experimental observation that the interchange energy varies exponentially with temperature is found to be in accord with theory.

Interchange energy is an important parameter in the theory of strictly regular solutions¹. Recently Rastogi and Nigam² have suggested from the analysis of solid-liquid equilibrium data that interchange energy varies exponentially with temperature. It is the purpose of this communication to examine how far this finding is theoretically justified.

Interchange Energy and Coefficient of Volume Expansion

According to the theory of strictly regular mixtures, the interchange energy, w , is given by

$$w = \frac{1}{2} N Z \cdot \{ \epsilon_{12} - \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22}) \} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{12} , ϵ_{11} , and ϵ_{22} are the pair-energies between molecules 1 and 2, 1 and 1, and 2 and 2 respectively; N is the Avogadro number and Z is the co-ordination number. If we use Sutherland's model as an approximation

$$\epsilon_{ik} = - \frac{\epsilon_{ik}^*}{r_{ik}^n} \quad \left(\begin{array}{l} i=1,2 \\ k=1,2 \end{array} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{ik}^* and n are constants; r_{ik} is the intermolecular separation. For the case of regular mixtures, we may assume $r_{11} = r_{12} = r_{22}$ and

$$\frac{dr_{11}}{dT} = \frac{dr_{12}}{dT} = \frac{dr_{22}}{dT}$$

Then,

$$w = - \frac{NZ}{r_{11}^n} \cdot \{ \epsilon_{12}^* - \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{11}^* + \epsilon_{22}^*) \} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Now, the interchange energy can change with temperature on account of variation in volume and also in the co-ordination number. Accordingly we have,

$$\frac{dw}{dT} = \frac{n}{r_{11}^{n+1}} \cdot NZ \cdot \{ \epsilon_{12}^* - \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{11}^* + \epsilon_{22}^*) \} \cdot \frac{dr_{11}}{dT} - \frac{NZ}{r_{11}^n} \cdot \{ \epsilon_{12}^* - \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{11}^* + \epsilon_{22}^*) \} \cdot \frac{dZ}{dT} \quad (4)$$

1. Guggenheim, "Mixtures", Oxford University Press, 1952; Prigogine, "Molecular Theory of Solutions", North-Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1957.
2. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, 55, 2005.

and hence,

$$\frac{d \ln w}{dT} = -\frac{n}{r_{11}} \cdot \frac{dr_{11}}{dT} + \frac{d \ln Z}{dT} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

If the volume, V , of the component 1 is put equal to $K \cdot r_{11}^3$, where K is a proportionality constant, the coefficient of volume expansion, α , would be given by

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{V} \cdot \frac{dV}{dT} = \frac{3}{r_{11}} \cdot \frac{dr_{11}}{dT} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The interchange energy may change with temperature at constant pressure or at constant volume. Corresponding to these, we have

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_P = -\frac{n}{3} \cdot \alpha + \left(\frac{\delta \ln Z}{\delta T}\right)_P \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_V = \left(\frac{\delta \ln Z}{\delta T}\right)_V \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

The co-ordination number at different temperatures can be estimated from the area under the peaks in the radial distribution curves obtained from X-ray data. From all available evidence it appears that Z decreases with increase in temperature for most of the substances and $(\delta \ln Z / \delta T)_P$ is likely to be much smaller than the coefficient of volume expansion. Hence both $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_P$ and $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_V$ would have negative sign. Thus, to a first approximation,

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_P \approx -\frac{n}{3} \cdot \alpha \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The coefficient of volume expansion may be treated as constant since it does not vary appreciably with temperature. Thus, equation (9) shows that w would increase exponentially with decrease in temperature, which is in agreement with experiment. In the solid phase Z is not likely to change with temperature and hence,

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_P = -\frac{n}{3} \cdot \alpha \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

From equation (3), it follows that the interchange energy in the solid phase would be greater than that in the liquid phase since in general $(r_{11})_{\text{liq.}} > (r_{11})_{\text{sol.}}$ and $Z_{\text{sol.}} > Z_{\text{liq.}}$, where the subscripts sol. and liq. refer to the solid and liquid phases respectively. This conclusion is also in accord with the experimental data³.

Comparison with Experimental Data

$(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_P$ can be evaluated from (i) G^E , the excess Gibbs function obtained from vapour pressure data of suitable mixtures at several temperatures, (ii) heat of mixing data at several temperatures, (iii) solid-liquid equilibrium data³, and (iv) heat of mixing and G^E at the same temperature. The last method is discussed below as it is not so obvious.

If we take into consideration the temperature dependence of interchange energy, the excess Gibbs function, G^E , and the excess heat function, H^E , at the same temperature are given by

$$G^E = x_1 x_2 w$$

and

$$H^E = x_1 x_2 \left(w - T \cdot \frac{dw}{dT} \right)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mole-fractions of the two components. Further, since $G^E = H^E - TS^E$, it follows that

$$\left(\frac{d \ln w}{dT} \right)_T = - \frac{S^E}{G^E} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

where S^E is the excess entropy of mixing.

The values of $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_T$ obtained from experimental data, as outlined above, are compared in Table I with the theoretical values calculated from equation (9) for several systems which are known to be regular. n has been assumed to be equal to 6 as is usually done.

TABLE I

System.	Temp.	$\left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T} \right)_T \right\}$ (deg. ⁻¹) _{exp.}	$\left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T} \right)_T \right\}$ (deg. ⁻¹) _{theor.}
Benzene—CCl ₄	-23.0°	-2.62 × 10 ⁻³ (a)	-2.280 × 10 ⁻³ (f)
	30.0°	-3.50 × 10 ⁻³ (b)	-2.486 × 10 ⁻³ (f)
Cyclohexane—CCl ₄	30.0°	-1.90 × 10 ⁻³ (b)	-2.486 × 10 ⁻³ (f)
CHCl ₃ —CCl ₄	40.0°	-4.10 × 10 ⁻³ (c)	-2.670 × 10 ⁻³ (g)
SiCl ₄ —CCl ₄	25.0°	-2.20 × 10 ⁻³ (d)	-2.486 × 10 ⁻³ (f) (at 30°)
Diphenylacetylene—diphenylethylene	65-105°	-6.10 × 10 ⁻³ (a)	..
Benzene—diphenyl	70.0°	-2.3 × 10 ⁻³ (e)	-2.646 × 10 ⁻³ (g)

(a) Calculated from the data obtained by Rastogi and Nigam.³

(b) Computed from Guggenheim's analysis of the data.¹

(c) Computed from the data of McGlashan *et al.*⁴

(d) Computed from the data of Wood⁵ and Vold⁶ with the help of equation (11).

(e) Computed from the data of Everett and Penny⁷ and Adcock and McGlashan⁸ with the help of eq. (11).

(f) For calculating these the values of α for CCl₄ as adopted by Rowlinson⁹ have been used.

(g) For calculating these, the values of α of chloroform and benzene as determined by Staveley *et al.*¹⁰ have been used.

4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 1284.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1510.

6. *Ibid.*, 1937, **59**, 1515.

7. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1952, **212A**, 164.

8. *Ibid.*, 1954, **226A**, 266.

9. "Liquids and Liquid Mixtures", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1959, p. 37.

10. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 323.

The agreement between the last two columns of Table I is satisfactory, considering the nature of approximations involved. The value of α for diphenylacetylene or diphenylethylene in the liquid phase was not available, hence no comparison could be made, but the value of $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_P$ appeared to be of the correct order of magnitude. Thus, it turns out that the interchange energy varies with temperature mainly on account of increase in volume at constant pressure. This fact had also been emphasised earlier¹¹.

It would be interesting to examine the temperature dependence of interchange energy for solutions of macro-molecules. Gee and collaborators have found that the vapour pressure data for solutions of rubber in benzene are best fitted by choosing the value of $w/kT = 0.43$, where k is the Boltzmann constant. Heat of mixing measurements are in agreement with theory¹¹ when $w/kT = 0.49$. Using equation (11), $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_P$ is found to be equal to -4.7×10^{-4} at 25°, whereas the coefficient of volume expansion for benzene is of the order of 2×10^{-3} .

In the above discussion, it has been assumed that the increase in temperature is always accompanied by the increase in the lattice distance or the intermolecular separation in the liquid phase. The fact is that there is a possibility of a decrease in the number of holes in the liquid with temperature. It is difficult to decide which factor would predominate.

We may examine the above considerations by using a more exact thermodynamic argument. By the usual methods of partial differentiation, it can be shown that

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln G^E}{\delta T}\right)_P = -\left(\frac{\delta \ln G^E}{\delta T}\right)_V + V \left(\frac{\delta \ln G^E}{\delta V}\right)_T \cdot \alpha \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

when it is assumed that the coefficient of volume expansion and molar volumes of pure components and the mixture are identical. When the interchange energy is defined by the equation $G^E = x_1 x_2 w$, we have

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_P = -\left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta T}\right)_V + V \cdot \left(\frac{\delta \ln w}{\delta V}\right)_T \cdot \alpha \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

The proportionality of $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_P$ with α can only be obtained if $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_V$ is zero and $V \cdot (\delta \ln w / \delta V)_T$ is constant. In general, $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_V$ is not zero although on the basis of the model used in the present discussion, $(\delta \ln w / \delta \ln V)_T$ would be a constant.

Comparison with the Theory of Conformal Solutions

The theory of conformal solutions¹² also yields the exponential dependence of interchange energy with temperature. Rowlinson¹³ has shown that the results of the

11. Scott, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 15, 44; Guggenheim, *ibid.*, 1953, 15, 24; Everett, *ibid.*, 1953, 15, 252

12. Longuet-Higgins, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1951, 205A, 247.

13. *Ibid.*, 1952, 214A, 102.

theory are applicable to lattice-model as well. Retaining only the first order terms, the theory of Longuet-Higgins¹² gives

$$\frac{SE}{QE} = \frac{R + (C_p)_{\text{config}}}{L_o - RT} \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

Using equation (11), we have

$$\frac{d \ln w}{dT} = - \frac{R + (C_p)_{\text{config}}}{L_o - RT} \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

where L_o is the latent heat of vaporisation and $(C_p)_{\text{config}}$ is the configurational heat capacity. Since, in general, RT is much less than L_o , $(d \ln w / dT)$ would be directly proportional to configurational heat capacity. Since $(C_p)_{\text{config}}$ changes very little with temperature, exponential dependence of w on temperature would be obtained. Further, a large part of $(C_p)_{\text{config}}$ is proportional to α and hence equation (9) and equation (15) can be shown to be equivalent. Employing equation (15) and using the appropriate values of configurational heat capacities¹³ and the latent heat of vaporisation¹⁴, $(\delta \ln w / \delta T)_F$ was found to be 2.22×10^{-3} at 30° for benzene- CCl_4 and cyclohexane- CCl_4 systems. These agree well with the values calculated from equation (9).

Equation (15) is theoretically more sound than equation (9) since for the latter Sutherland's model has been used which is a little artificial in the sense that it does not allow the molecules to perform harmonic oscillations even at the lowest temperatures.

From the above discussion, it may be concluded that equation (9) can be used as a good and useful approximation for evaluating the temperature dependence of interchange energy.

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14. Timmermans, "Physico-Chemical Constants of Organic Compounds", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1950.